

Chemotherapy Explained: A Realistic Guide for Patients and Caregivers

From Asst.Prof.Dr. Ahmet Sami Bosnak

Chapter 1. Understanding Chemotherapy Cycles

The moment you're told you need chemotherapy, you'll start hearing things like:

“We'll give 3 cycles of treatment,”

“Your scans will be done after the 4th cycle,”

“What cycle are you on?”,

“My nausea got better after the 2nd cycle, yours will too,” and so on.

But what exactly is a “**Cycle**”?

How Cycles Work?

The chemotherapy protocol chosen for you is structured as repeated cycles.

For example, the **AC protocol** (Adriablastin + Cyclophosphamide), which is one of the most commonly prescribed regimens for breast cancer, consists of **4 cycles repeated every 21 days**. (1)

- Day 1 of the first hospital visit = completion of the 1st cycle.
- The next appointment is scheduled 21 days later for the 2nd cycle.
- The same drugs are given again, and the 3rd cycle follows 21 days later.
- After the 4th cycle, various tests and scans are performed to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment.

Not all regimens are this simple. Some protocols — especially for advanced-stage breast cancer — may involve **up to 13 cycles**. (2)

For example:

- The first 4 cycles are AC (the same as above).
- On the 5th cycle, Trastuzumab is given on Day 1, and the patient is asked to return the **next day** instead of after 21 days.
- On Day 2 of the 5th cycle, Paclitaxel is administered.
- On the 6th cycle, both drugs are given together on the same day.
- From the 9th cycle onwards, only Trastuzumab is given every 21 days.
- After completing 13 cycles (approximately 1 year), the treatment is finished and tests are repeated.

Common Misunderstandings

One frequent problem arises when patients are told, “You will receive 4 cycles of treatment,” but if a single cycle involves 2 consecutive treatment days, they mistakenly believe they have completed their therapy after 4 **days** of hospital visits.

This confusion can seriously affect **treatment adherence**. When patients return expecting to be “done” but are scheduled for more chemotherapy, they may lose trust or motivation. That’s why it’s crucial for patients to understand what “cycle” means. Sticking to scheduled appointment dates is also extremely important.

Why Timing Between Cycles Matters

In the example above, there are 21 days between cycles — sometimes this can be as short as 7 days depending on the protocol.

Why not 19 or 25 days?

Chemotherapy protocols are the result of long, rigorous research. These drugs are designed to **kill cancer cells** while causing minimal harm to healthy cells. But drug design alone isn’t enough — **how the drug is administered** plays a critical role in its effectiveness.

The **break between cycles** allows your body to recover and prepare for the next treatment. Most chemotherapy drugs affect dividing cells. Since cancer cells divide rapidly and uncontrollably, the drugs target them most effectively in the 24–48 hours following infusion. Cells not dividing in that window are targeted in the 2nd, 3rd, or later cycles.

That’s why scans and lab tests are done **after completing all cycles**, not after each one. It’s the most rational way to evaluate true treatment response.

What About Healthy Cells?

You might wonder: *“If the drugs affect dividing cells, don’t they also affect my healthy cells?”*

Yes, most current chemotherapy drugs still affect healthy cells too. But there’s a crucial difference: **healthy cells can repair themselves** during the rest periods, whereas cancer cells can’t.

This is why the treatment alternates between **drug administration and recovery periods** — gradually destroying cancer cells while allowing your body to heal.

(1) [BC Cancer – BRAJAC Protocol](#)

(2) [BC Cancer – BRAJACTT Protocol](#)